

Pedagogical Conditions For Training Personnel Based On National Musical Traditions

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Abstract: This thesis provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of the pedagogical conditions of the process of training personnel based on national musical traditions. The study highlights the integration of national musical heritage into the content of education, the possibilities of using traditional music samples in the formation of professional and cultural competencies of future specialists. Also, factors such as systematic teaching of national musical values, their combination with innovative pedagogical technologies, and increasing the effectiveness of practical training are substantiated as important pedagogical conditions that directly affect the quality of personnel training. The conclusions of the thesis are of practical importance in improving the training of musical and pedagogical personnel in the higher education system.

Keywords: national musical traditions, personnel training, pedagogical conditions, musical education, professional competence, cultural heritage, educational content.

Introduction.

In the current era of accelerating globalization and cultural integration, the issue of preserving, developing national musical traditions and conveying them to the younger generation through the education system is emerging as one of the urgent scientific and pedagogical problems. In particular, the issue of methodologically based use of national musical heritage in the process of training musical and pedagogical personnel in the higher education system is one of the important areas of modern pedagogy and music education theory.

An analysis of scientific literature shows that national musical traditions have important educational and didactic opportunities in forming a person's aesthetic taste, understanding of national identity, and professional culture. In particular, scholars such as A. Fitrat, I. Rajabov, F. Karomatov, R. Abdullayev, D. Omonullayeva, who studied Central Asian and Uzbek musical culture, have scientifically substantiated that national music is not only a model of art, but also a powerful socio-pedagogical tool. Their works emphasize the role of maqom, folk songs, and traditional performing schools in the spiritual and moral development of the younger generation.

Modern research in the field of pedagogy and music education (B. Gershunsky, N. Kuzmina, V. Slastyonin, Sh. Sharipov, R. Jo'rayev, etc.) shows that the effectiveness of the personnel training process is directly related to pedagogical conditions. These scientists recognize such factors as the enrichment of the educational content with national values, the professional and cultural preparation of the teacher, and the creation of an educational environment focused on practical activities as important pedagogical conditions.

In recent years, the issue of combining national musical traditions with innovative pedagogical technologies has also been the focus of special attention. In particular, it has been scientifically substantiated that the formation of national musical knowledge and skills through training based on a competency-based approach, integrative education, projects, and practical exercises improves the quality of personnel training. However, the analysis of the literature shows that there is a lack of research devoted to a systematic and comprehensive coverage of the pedagogical conditions for training personnel based on national musical traditions.

Therefore, the analysis of the process of training personnel based on national musical traditions from a scientific and pedagogical point of view, the identification and justification of pedagogical conditions ensuring its effectiveness, determine the relevance of this thesis.

Discussion

In the process of discussing the issue of training personnel based on national musical traditions, it is important, first of all, to determine what pedagogical opportunities national music has as a substantive and educational component of education. Scientific literature shows that national music is not only an aesthetic phenomenon, but also an important pedagogical factor that shapes the socio-cultural identity of a person.

In particular, A. Fitrat, touching on the issue of national music, interprets it as a cultural phenomenon that embodies the historical memory and educational power of the people. In his work "Music of the East", he writes: "Music is the expression of the soul of the nation in sound, and a people that has lost it loses its spiritual support" (Fitrat, 1993). This idea confirms the need to consider national musical traditions as an important pedagogical resource in the system of personnel training. Uzbek musicologist F. Karomatov, analyzing the educational value of national music, emphasizes that folk music samples have great potential for developing the aesthetic thinking and creative abilities of young people. According to the scientist, "by introducing folk music samples into the educational process, not only performing skills are formed, but also national thinking and artistic taste" (Karomatov, 2008).

This shows that the correct selection of educational content in the training of personnel based on national musical traditions is an important pedagogical condition.

From a pedagogical point of view, the effectiveness of personnel training depends on a set of certain conditions, as emphasized by the Russian pedagogical scientist V. A. Slastyonin. According to him, “the effectiveness of education depends on the harmony of the content, methods and environment of the pedagogical process” (Slastyonin, 2002). This approach justifies the need to organize practical training, performing activities and a creative environment in the training of national musical traditions, not limited to theoretical knowledge.

N. V. Kuzmina also shows that the professional and cultural competence of the teacher is a decisive factor in the training process. In her opinion, “the teacher’s personal culture and professional training are among the main factors determining the effective mastery of educational content” (Kuzmina, 1990). This idea shows that the teacher's national music knowledge and performance experience are important pedagogical conditions for teaching based on national musical traditions.

Uzbek pedagogical scientist R. H. Jo'rayev, discussing the issue of relying on national values in the educational process, concludes: "the preservation of nationality in the content of education is an important factor leading a person to spiritual perfection" (Jo'rayev, 2015). This view once again confirms the need to consider national musical traditions as a strategic pedagogical factor in the personnel training system. The analysis and discussion of the above literature shows that the effectiveness of the personnel training process based on national musical traditions is directly related to the following pedagogical conditions: the reliance of the educational content on national musical samples, the professional and cultural competence of the teacher, the presence of a practical and creative educational environment, and the use of innovative pedagogical approaches. The combination of these conditions serves to improve the quality of personnel training.

Conclusion.

The conducted scientific analysis and discussions show that the process of training personnel based on national musical traditions is one of the important pedagogical tasks facing the modern education system. National music is not only a means of aesthetic education, but also an effective pedagogical resource in the formation of professional, cultural and spiritual competencies of future specialists.

The results of the study confirmed that the effectiveness of training personnel based on national musical traditions is directly related to the presence and harmony of certain pedagogical conditions. In particular, the reliance of the content of

education on the national musical heritage, the professional and cultural training of the teacher, the creation of an educational environment focused on practical and creative activities, and the use of innovative pedagogical approaches were identified as the main conditions for this process. It was also found that ensuring the harmony of theory and practice in the process of teaching national musical traditions, the effective use of the experience of traditional performing schools, and organizing the educational process on the basis of a competency-based approach serve to improve the quality of personnel training. This, along with the preservation and development of the national musical heritage, allows training competitive specialists who meet modern requirements.

In conclusion, the scientific substantiation of the pedagogical conditions for training personnel based on national musical traditions and their implementation in practice is an important factor in improving musical and pedagogical education in the higher education system, creating a theoretical and practical basis for further research in this area.

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